

THE EFFECT OF IMPACT DAMAGE ON THE DYNAMIC PROPERTIES OF
LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATES

John J. Tracy*, David J. Dimas**, Gerard C. Pardoen***

*McDonnell Douglas Astronautics Company
Huntington Beach, California, 92647, USA

**PDA Engineering
Santa Ana, California, 92705, USA

***Associate Professor, Civil Engineering
University of California, Irvine
Irvine, California, 92715, USA

Summary

In this study, modal analysis techniques were used to investigate the effect of impact damage on the dynamic properties of advanced composite materials. Four laminated graphite-epoxy plates were fabricated using various fiber types and stacking sequences. A Hewlett-Packard 5423A Structural Dynamics Analyzer was used to determine the dynamic signatures of the plates before testing. The plates were then impacted with a 1/2-inch-diameter projectile traveling up to 138 feet per second. The damaged laminates were once again analyzed with the HP 5423A system, and the frequencies, damping, and mode shapes were compared with those of the pretest plates. The impact damage caused reductions in frequencies for selected modes. The test results were corroborated with finite-element analyses of both the pretest and posttest plates.

Introduction and Background

Advanced composite materials such as graphite epoxy and Kevlar epoxy offer several advantages for structures which require a combination of high strength/stiffness with low weight. However, these materials are, in general, significantly more brittle than their metal counterparts. Also, in contrast to their in-plane properties, transverse tensile and interlaminar shear strengths of composite laminates are quite low (1-7). As a consequence, advanced composite materials are susceptible to damage from low velocity impact.

Low velocity impacts can substantially reduce both the strength and stiffness of advanced composite materials, without any external signs of the damage being visible (8-11). Existing nondestructive test techniques such as ultrasonic C-scan, radiography, and vibrothermography, can only identify internal damage qualitatively (12-15). A nondestructive inspection technique is needed which will give quantitative information about the effects of the impact damage on the structural performance of the composite. This paper describes how experimental modal analysis techniques can be used to identify the effects of impact on the dynamic response of advanced composite materials.

Since the advent of inexpensive, two channel, digital Fourier analyzers in the early 1970's, the use of modal analysis as a non-destructive test technique has been studied by several researchers. Investigators from various fields are all attracted to modal based techniques since, theoretically, access to only a single, arbitrary point on the structure is necessary. This advantage has been successfully exploited to detect damage in inaccessible regions of several structures. Coppolino and Rubin (16,17) and also Shahrivar and colleagues (18) used the modal technique to detect structural damage in the submerged portions of offshore oil platforms. West (19) used the modal method to inspect the internal structure (inaccessible due to thermal protection tiles) of a body flap from the Shuttle Orbiter. With no prior knowledge of the damage, West detected structural damage that had not been detected by conventional visual, x-ray, and ultrasonic inspections.

Researchers investigating modal based NDT methods on advanced composites have not attempted to analyze structures with the complexity of those described above. Adams (20) studied changes in natural frequencies and damping caused by torsional static and fatigue loading on both graphite epoxy and glass epoxy unidirectional tubes. Gibson (21) progressively damaged cross-ply E-glass beams with large amplitude vibration and determined changes in damping and natural frequency. Gibson found that microstructural damage could cause as great as 350% increase in damping while reducing the natural frequencies by 5% or less. Adams (22) used frequency shifts of longitudinal modes in glass epoxy tubes to detect and locate damage which was equivalent to a 1% reduction of tube cross sectional area. Cawley (23,24), extending the work of Adams to two dimensions, used modal analysis combined with the finite element method to detect and locate localized crushing, holes and saw cuts in cross-ply and angle-ply graphite epoxy plates. Using a more complicated structure, Reddy (25) studied the effects of progressive stiffener removal on the natural frequencies of composite isogrid panels.

In this study four 13-by 12-inch laminated graphite-epoxy panels were, fabricated using various stacking sequences and fiber types. Broadband and zoom transform frequency response measurements of each laminate were obtained with a Hewlett-Packard 5423A Structural Dynamics Analyzer. An

electromagnetic shaker was used to excite the plates with white noise. With the shaker location kept stationary, a small accelerometer was used to measure the response at 36 points on the surface of each plate. The resulting frequency response measurements were curve-fit, and modal parameters for the undamaged plates were determined. Subsequent to the modal identification of these plates, each of the plates was impacted with 1/2-inch-diameter aluminum spheres at velocities between 107 and 138 feet per second. Damage was generated in each of the plates in varying degrees. All plates were then analyzed again with the modal procedure.

Finite-element analysis was used throughout the study to determine the frequency ranges where shifts were likely to occur. Once the experimental data was collected, the analysis was also used to verify the experimental mode shapes. These results were validated with finite-element models, which included simulated impact damage.

Finite Element Analysis

The equation of motion for the free vibration behavior of a thin, orthotropic, symmetrical, rectangular plate is

$$D_{11} (\partial^4 w / \partial x^4) + 2 (D_{12} + 2D_{33}) (\partial^4 w / \partial x^2 \partial y^2) + D_{22} (\partial^4 w / \partial y^4) = m (\partial^2 w / \partial t^2) \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) cannot usually be solved for the frequencies and mode shapes because the equation is complicated, being subject to a variety of potential boundary conditions. Accordingly, an approximate technique, such as the finite-element method, must be used to calculate the natural frequencies and modes. The usual finite-element strategy is to determine the frequencies and modes from the eigenvalue equation

$$\det (\underline{K} - \omega^2 \underline{M}) = 0 \quad (2)$$

The stiffness matrix \underline{K} is derived from the strain energy expression

$$\begin{aligned} & 1/2 \int_0^a \int_0^b [D_{11} (\partial^2 w / \partial x^2)^2 + D_{22} (\partial^2 w / \partial y^2)^2 + 4D_{33} (\partial^2 w / \partial x \partial y)^2 \\ & + 2D_{12} (\partial^2 w / \partial x^2) (\partial^2 w / \partial y^2)] dx dy \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

whereas the mass matrix \underline{M} is derived from the kinetic energy expression

$$1/2 \int_0^b \int_0^a m (\partial w / \partial t)^2 dx dy \quad (4)$$

A finite-element model was developed to predict the free-free vibration modes for the four plates both before and after impact. These analyses were performed to provide guidance to the experimental procedure by predicting which resonant frequencies exhibited a significant decrease in magnitude. The numerical analysis also provided verification of the experimental results.

The MSC/NASTRAN (26) computer code was used to extract the frequencies and mode shapes for the four composite plates. The analytical

model consisted of 144 QUAD4 plate elements spanning 169 nodes. The total number of degrees of freedom was 507. Comparison with a model having more than six times the number of degrees of freedom revealed no significant differences in the results; accordingly, it was felt that it was reasonable to use the above model to assess the modes for the undamaged plates.

The damaged plates were simulated by removing two elements from the center of the plate model. The size of the area removed corresponded roughly to the damaged area as indicated by the C-scan results.

Experimental Procedure

The composite laminates used were fabricated from unidirectional Thornel T300/5208 and T50/5208 graphite-epoxy prepreg. Stiffness properties for the unidirectional materials (Table I) were taken from References (27,28) and it should be noted that the properties given for the T50 material are properties of generic high-modulus-fiber composites. No properties testing was conducted on the T50 material. Limited properties testing conducted on the T300 material (high-strength fiber) showed that the generic values could be off by more than 20 percent; analytical results on panels with the T50 material were, therefore, viewed with caution.

TABLE I
Unidirectional Ply Stiffness Properties

Material	E_L (psi)	E_T (psi)	G_{LT} (psi)	ν_{LT}	Thickness (in.)	Density (lb/in. ³)
T300/5208	20.4×10^6	1.42×10^6	0.79×10^6	.181	.00556	1.466×10^{-4}
T50/5208	25.0×10^6	1.70×10^6	0.650×10^6	.300	.00469	1.533×10^{-4}

Variation in ply orientation was used to give each of the plates its own characteristic bending stiffness. All ply stacking sequences were arranged so that the 16 plies would be symmetric about the midplane of the plate. This was done to prevent any extensional and bending coupling. Classical laminated plate theory (6) was used to calculate laminate extensional and bending stiffnesses from the unidirectional ply properties. Table II gives the stacking sequence, thickness, and principal bending stiffnesses for each of the plates. The D_{11} and D_{22} values are the bending stiffnesses in the 13- and 12-inch directions, respectively. D_{33} gives the plate resistance to twisting. Notice that plates 1 and 2 have extremely low twisting stiffness. This is a result of the fact that neither laminate has any 45-degree plies. The effect of the lack of twisting stiffness will be the presence of very-low-frequency torsional modes in plates 1 and 2. Plates 1 through 3 were fabricated with T300/5208 prepreg. Plate 4 was fabricated from high-modulus T50/5208 prepreg. It was intended that this be the stiffest plate of the four made. However, during the fabrication process, plate 4 became resin poor, which resulted in a thinner laminate than the expected 0.09 inch. Inasmuch as the bending stiffnesses are proportional to the cube of the thickness, the fact that plate 4 had a thickness of only 0.08 inch made it the most flexible of the plates.

Table II
Laminate Configuration

Plate	Stacking Sequence	Thickness (in.)	D ₁₁ (in.-lb.)	D ₂₂ (in.-lb.)	D ₃₃ (in.-lb.)
1	[(0,90) ₄]sym	.09	747.	537.	47.
2	[(90,0 ₂) ₂ ,(90,0)]sym	.09	683.	600.	46.
3	[(0,±45,90) ₂]sym	.09	593.	436.	174.
4	[(0,±45,90) ₂]sym	.08	434.	317.	120.

A low-pressure compressed-air launch tube was used to impact each of the plates with 1/2-inch-diameter aluminum spheres. Initially, all the plates were impacted at a velocity of 107 feet per second. Plates 1, 2, and 3 showed no visible signs of damage. Plate 4 had a small amount of visible damage on the back surface beneath the impactor. Because the goal was to produce barely visible damage, plates 1, 2, and 3 were impacted again in the same location but at 138 feet per second. This produced small, visible damage areas (small with respect to the projectile's diameter) on the back surface of each of the plates. None of the plates showed any visible sign of damage on the front surface. Plate 4 had the greatest amount of impact damage. There was a permanent deformation 0.5 inch in diameter evident on the back surface of the plate. Plate 3 had a damage region on the back surface that was 0.5 by 0.05 inch. This crack ran parallel to the long axis of the plate and, not surprisingly, parallel to the fiber direction in the back-surface ply. Plate 2 had a crack similar to the one found in plate 3. The crack was directed along the short axis of the plate, which was also the fiber direction for the back-surface ply. Plate 1 showed the least damage of all the plates. There was a very slight crease that appeared to be no deeper than the surface ply. The crease was about 1 inch long and oriented in the direction of the fibers of the back-surface ply.

Ultrasonic C-scan was used to determine the amount of internal damage generated in each of the plates. In general, the internal damage covered about twice the area of the visible external damage. However, it should be noted that the ultrasonic technique only records the attenuation of the sound waves as they pass through the material. The size of the damage area measured can change substantially based upon the level of attenuation selected for triggering by the operator. In fact, it was this somewhat arbitrary component of the C-scan procedure that motivated the investigation of modal analysis as an NDI tool.

Modal Analysis

During the past few years experimental modal analysis (EMA) has emerged as an important technique in the area of structural dynamic testing. Experimental modal analysis is a procedure to determine from empirical data the dynamic characteristics of a structure. These modal parameters are 1) resonant frequencies, 2) vibrational mode shape, and 3) damping. The underlying assumptions of this technique are 1) the structure can be modeled by a system of second order differential equations, 2) the system is linear (modes of vibration are only defined in linear systems), and 3) the system must obey Maxwell-Betti reciprocity (the structure is symmetric with respect to its dynamic properties). The

algorithms involved in experimental modal analysis rely heavily upon use of the Fourier transform. Although the fast Fourier transform algorithm has been available since the early 60s it was not until the advent of the hardwired fast Fourier transform that experimental modal analysis became cost competitive with analytical techniques. In this study a Hewlett-Packard 5423A Structural Dynamic Analyzer was used to provide hardwired fast Fourier transform computations and other processing capabilities such as curve-fitting techniques and 3-D animated graphic displays.

The modal test methodology begins by exciting the vibrational modes of the structure. This can be accomplished by various techniques depending on the application. The more common excitation techniques include 1) random vibration, 2) sine dwell or sine sweep, and 3) impulsive (usually performed by striking the structure with an instrumented hammer). The response of the structure, caused by the excitation force, is measured at various locations on the structure (the response measured is normally acceleration or displacement). A hardwired fast Fourier transformation is performed on both the input and the response signals for each of the selected response points on the structure. Dividing the FFT of the output by the FFT of the input yields the system transfer function. This transfer function is displayed and modes of interest are selected. An analytical single degree of freedom system is then curve fit to the experimental transfer function in the area of each selected mode. This curve fitting yields the modal parameters of frequency, mode shape and damping. This test methodology is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1.

MODAL TEST METHODOLOGY

1. EXCITE MODES
2. MEASURE INPUT AND RESPONSE SIGNAL
3. CONSTRUCT FREQUENCY RESPONSE FUNCTION BY FFT TECHNIQUES
4. IDENTIFY PREDOMINANT MODES
5. CURVE FIT EXPERIMENTAL DATA TO DETERMINE MODAL DAMPING

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In this study response measurements were taken at 36 points on each laminate. Once the transfer function for each of the locations had been obtained, the measurement that appeared to possess all the modes of interest was selected and curve-fit to yield the modal parameters. As mentioned above, in order to determine the modal damping coefficient and the residues (for mode shapes), a single-degree-of-freedom analytical transfer function was mathematically matched to the experimental data. This analytical transfer function for a single mode of vibration can be written in partial fraction form as

$$H(s) = \frac{r}{2j(s-p)} - \frac{r^*}{2j(s-p^*)} \quad (5)$$

where

- s = Laplace variable = $j\omega$
- r = residue
- p = pole location
- ω = natural frequency (rad/sec)
- * = denotes complex conjugate

The HP 5243A analyzer uses a polynomial representation of the above equation evaluated as a frequency response function (i.e., for $s = j\omega$). A least-square curve fit is then calculated according to the relation

$$E = \sum_{i=1}^m |h_i - H(j\omega)_i|^2$$

where

- $H(j\omega)_i$ = the analytical function
- h_i = the experimental data

The above modal testing procedure was repeated identically for each of the four plates both before and after impact testing. A broadband random signal was initially used to excite the vibrational modes and determine the modal parameters for each laminate configuration. A zoom transform technique was used to more accurately quantify these parameters in frequency bands in which shifts in resonant frequencies occurred. The finite-element analysis of the posttest and pretest plates was used to determine these frequency ranges.

The broadband random signal was produced by a waveform generator over a frequency range of 20 to 20,000 Hz. This signal drove a permanent magnet vibration exciter rated at 10 lbf. A quartz force transducer was placed between the stinger of the vibration exciter and the plate. A single accelerometer was sequentially placed at each grid point on the plate to measure the response. The stinger of the vibration exciter was located in such a way as to excite both symmetric and antisymmetric modes. The plates were mounted on soft pads to simulate free-free boundary conditions.

During the test, an ensemble of 30 excitation/response measurements was taken at each grid point and averaged. This was done in order to ensure a statistically reliable result. After each ensemble of measurements was averaged, the coherence was checked before the accelerometer was moved to the next point.

Results

To initially check the experimental and analytical procedure, a comparison was made between the finite-element results and the experimental results for undamaged plate 3. As shown in Table III there is good agreement between the analytical and experimental results. The NASTRAN analysis over estimated several frequencies by 1 to 7 percent.

It should be noted that some modes indicated by the NASTRAN analysis did not appear in the experimental results. Also, some closely spaced modes were compressed into a single mode in the experimental data. In addition, any mode that had a node at the shaker input would not show up in the data due to the single-point driving method used.

Mode shapes were generated for the first symmetric and antisymmetric bending modes (Figure 2). The experimental mode shapes were generated directly from the frequency response functions by the HP 5423A. The analytical mode shapes were generated from the NASTRAN results with the PDA/PATRAN-G (29) pre- and postprocessing system. The experimental mode shapes were the purest at the lower frequencies. Better high-frequency mode shapes can be achieved by simply zooming in closer to the frequency of interest. Inasmuch as this study was primarily concerned with frequency shifts between damaged and undamaged plates, higher-order mode shapes were not investigated thoroughly.

A comparison of the modal data before and after the plates were impacted shows that each plate had substantial frequency reductions in certain modes between 900 and 1400 Hz. These results were verified by comparing FEM solutions for undamaged plates with those of FEM models with simulated damage. In both the analytical and experimental results, several modes were reduced by 1 to 5 Hz by the damage. Only one or two modes were reduced in frequency by 15 Hz or more.

Plate 4 was found to have two natural frequencies that were substantially affected by the impact damage. Figure 3 shows two frequency response functions (transfer functions) from plate 4 taken at the same measurement point. The dashed line shows the response of the undamaged plate, while the solid line shows the response after damage. The two frequencies, which were originally at 952 and 1235 Hz, were reduced by 15 and 19 Hz, respectively.

Plate 3 also exhibited two substantial frequency reductions. Figure 4 shows the damaged and undamaged frequency response functions at a typical measurement point. Natural frequencies of 1125 and 1388 Hz showed shifts downward of 35 and 31 Hz, respectively. Plate 2 had only one mode that was substantially reduced in frequency. A mode originally at 1221 Hz was reduced to 1138 Hz. Figure 5 compares two frequency response functions for plate 2 before and after the impact event.

No substantial changes were found in the frequency response functions of plate 1. The NASTRAN analysis did indicate a shifted mode at about 800 Hz, but none was detected. Failure to detect a shift in this plate indicates that either the damaged region was not modeled accurately enough in the analysis or that the resolution of the modal inspection technique was inadequate. Inasmuch as plate 1 showed less damage than the other plates, and given the fact that a simple hole was to model the damage in NASTRAN, incorrect analysis seems a likely reason. Another possibility is that the shifted mode occurred at the edge of two measurement ranges. Plate 1 was the first tested, and the pre-impact response functions were

collected using the zoom transform, but no frequency range overlap. This oversight was not repeated on any of the other panels.

Table III
Verification of Experimental Results by Comparison to
Analytical Predictions

Laminate 3	
Undamaged	
Analytical	Experimental
82.9 Hz	88.1 Hz
123.3 Hz	124.2 Hz
151.4 Hz	145.0 Hz
207.1 Hz	209.0 Hz
218.9 Hz	*
374.4 Hz	344.1 Hz
378.2 Hz	362.5 Hz
380.2 Hz	378.3 Hz
418.1 Hz	*
471.2 Hz	438.0 Hz
608.5 Hz	590.1 Hz
633.0 Hz	*
709.5 Hz	661.5 Hz
742.9 Hz	720.2 Hz
782.1 Hz	760.0 Hz
794.6 Hz	*
874.1 Hz	875.0 Hz
932.3 Hz	*
991.0 Hz	967.0 Hz
1175.0 Hz	1125.0 Hz
1181.8 Hz	1159.0 Hz
1193.3 Hz	1182.0 Hz
1202.0 Hz	1204.0 Hz
1241.0 Hz	1233.0 Hz
1268.1 Hz	*
1387.0 Hz	1388.0 Hz

*No corresponding experimental mode

Table IV gives both the experimental and analytical values for the modes that shifted in each plate. Figure 6 shows the analytical mode shapes for the shifted modes. All experimental mode shapes lacked a significant number of measurement points to accurately define the high-frequency deformations of the shifted modes. In addition, because inadequate zooming was used to define the higher-order modes, some grid points had residues that were inconsistent with the rest of the set.

Only one mode in plate 2 exhibited a major frequency reduction. This mode contained two full waves in the longitudinal direction and zero waves in the perpendicular direction. Both shifted modes in plate 3 had two full waves in each direction. For plate 4, the first shifted mode had approximately two full waves in each direction. The second shifted mode had approximately two and one-half full waves in each direction.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

EXPERIMENTALLY DERIVED
TRANSFER FUNCTION

Undamaged and Damaged Plate 4

Figure 4.

Undamaged and Damaged Plate 3

Figure 5.

Undamaged and Damaged Plate 2

Table IV
Summary of Results, Natural Frequencies

Laminate	Δf	Undamaged		Damaged	
		Experimental	Analytical	Experimental	Analytical
1		No significant experimental shifts identified			
2	38 Hz	1221.0 Hz	1274.0 Hz	1183.0 Hz	1238.0 Hz
3	35 Hz	1125.0 Hz	1175.0 Hz	1090.0 Hz	1154.0 Hz
	31 Hz	1388.0 Hz	1387.0 Hz	1357.0 Hz	1362.0 Hz
4	15 Hz	952.0 Hz	1061.0 Hz	937.0 Hz	1043.0 Hz
	19 Hz	1235.0 Hz	1251.0 Hz	1216.0 Hz	1228.0 Hz

Figure 6.

Analytical Mode Shapes For Shifted Modes

Measurement of damping factors and how they change with material damage was an intended part of this study. However, the damping values measured were in the range of 0.3 to 3.0 percent. While the majority of damping values measured were near 0.5 percent, several values were substantially larger. The high values were probably caused by the plate support foam. The damping values for about 80 percent of the modes did increase by as much as 20 percent after impact. Adams (20) et al., and Gibson (21) were able to establish a trend of the damping factor with damage in composites. The present study verified that trend but was unable to do more than that due to the high damping characteristics of the plate support system.

Discussion

Damage not visible from the impacted side of the plates and slightly visible from the back side caused changes in the bending characteristics of the plates. The damage regions did cause a small reduction in overall bending stiffness, as was evidenced by the very slight shifts (1 to 5 Hz) over the entire frequency range. However, large frequency shifts only occurred for higher-order bending modes.

When the damaged region was small with respect to the characteristic wavelength of the vibrational mode, the mode did not "feel" the effect of the damage to any extent. However, when the the size of damage zone was comparable to the characteristic wavelength, the effect was large. This phenomenon is plausible when viewed in terms of strain energy.

Higher-order bending modes have substantial amounts of strain energy stored in small regions. If the plate properties are changed even slightly in a local region, the strain energy distribution is altered substantially as is the plate's response. In lower-order bending modes, the energy state is smoothly distributed and substantially lower. Localized damage in these modes does not cause the same major redistribution of strain energy.

Conclusions

The modal inspection technique shows promise as a tool for determining the amount of impact damage present in composite structures. Frequency shifts of higher-order bending modes give a clear indication of the presence of impact damage. Continuing work is necessary to determine if the modal inspection technique can resolve fine variations in the amount and location of impact damage.

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